

Modeling Study on Die-to-Pad Ratio and Its Relationship with QFN Delamination

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I. OVERVIEW

- The continuing trend in IC (integrated circuit) packaging is miniaturization or package size reduction.
- However, there is also a need to increase die functionality and a larger die is being forced to fit in a smaller die pad and this results in higher die-to-pad ratio for QFN (quad flat no lead) package.
- Die-to-pad ratio (DPR) is the ratio of the die size to the leadframe die pad size as illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Die-to-pad ratio (DPR) calculation for a QFN package.

II. PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

- One common problem encountered with higher DPR is leadframe interface delamination and package crack as shown in Fig. 2.
- To better address this problem, there needs to be a better understanding of how higher DPR results in delamination and package crack.

Fig. 2. QFN package leadframe interface delamination and package crack.

III. FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

- Finite element modeling (Fig. 3) was used to study the relationship between DPR and interface stress.
- Mold-leadframe interface stress was extracted at a specific location considered to be the usual delamination initiation area based on failure analysis results.

Fig. 3. Finite element model of the QFN package analyzed.

IV. STRESS RESULTS AND THE RELATIONSHIP WITH DELAMINATION

- Based on the modeling results (Figs. 4-6), leadframe interface stress is higher with higher DPR.
- Higher interface stress means a higher tendency of the interface to delaminate.
- This relationship explains why delamination is usually encountered when the package design has higher DPR.
- The relationship between DPR and interface stress also appears to vary with package size.
- When interface delamination happens, package crack could also occur as delamination propagates along the interface.
- For designs with higher DPR (especially around DPR = 90%), some strong leadframe-mold anchoring and leadframe adhesion improvement are needed (e.g. anchoring holes, slots, leadframe roughening, surface treatment).

Fig. 4. Leadframe interface stress vs DPR for package size = 5 mm and 6 mm.

Fig. 5. Leadframe interface stress vs DPR for package size = 7 mm and 8 mm.

Fig. 6. Leadframe interface stress vs DPR for package size = 9 mm and 10 mm.